

JARGON AND SLANG AS A SIDE LAYER

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Annotation: Another form of social dialect is slang. The term jargon is also derived from the French language, and linguists and etymologists have different opinions about its meaning.

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Another form of social dialect is slang. The term jargon is also derived from the French language, and linguists and etymologists have different opinions about its meaning. For example, M. Fasmer derives the word "jargon" from the ancient Gallo-Roman language and means "to beat", A. D. Michelson connects it to the French word "jarz" (male goose), and A. Doza "gargouiller" (to torment) says. Linguist V. A. Khomyakov, relying on the opinion expressed by etymologist U. Skit, says that slang means mixed speech, the word slang in the French language means "bird's chirping". In general, slang refers to the speech of representatives of a certain group whose interests and occupations are close to each other. However, linguists of different nationalities treat jargon differently. That is, a certain decision has not yet been reached. For example, O.Espersen, E.Hemplar consider this concept as professional jargon, while L.I. Skvortsov, U.O'Grady evaluate it as a mysterious professional language, Sh.Bally as an incomprehensible mysterious language.

To fully understand the meaning of the term jargon, we refer to a number of sociolinguistic dictionaries. In the linguistic dictionary compiled by O.S.Akhmanova, this term is defined as follows: "It is usually used in an oral style and is used as a means of secret communication in a social group separated from the representatives of society," and in the sociolinguistic dictionary compiled by scientists of the Russian Academy of Sciences, it is said: "... is a lexical or phraseological unit, used as group slang. Observed in a more verbal style, it is contrasted with the speech of the 'own' group and with the speech of the other group. In the dictionary compiled by American sociolinguists, slang is defined as: "1) It is considered the initial form of pidgin and does not have a clear structure. It is a language of a small group because it was formed in the process of work; 2) it is defined as a speech appearance that appears on the basis of professional interest between the owners of different professions, mainly in the types of training that require physical strength. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is said: "Words and phrases specific to a social or professional group, which only they understand and which differ from the literary language."

From the definitions and descriptions in dictionaries, it is clear that jargon is the speech of a certain professional group. The speech of a small circle of social groups and communities, whose interest or occupation is almost the same in terms of age, is the use of special words and phrases in their speech based on their own tastes and requirements or internal necessity and needs. In general, theoretically, one of the ideas complements, enriches, does not negate the other. However, the first definition given by American sociolinguists is somewhat

inappropriate in our view. Because slang cannot be the initial form of pidgin. Pidgin is a kind of new language that emerged as a result of the mixing of language elements of two independent languages due to various economic and political reasons. Jargon is the use of language elements in a different sense within the framework of a language, or a different name with the help of vague, empty - neological words that did not exist anywhere before.

Conducting consistent research on slang At the beginning of the 20th century, V. V. Vinogradov, B. A. Larin, A. M. Selishchev were among the first to study the influence of slang on the literary language. At the next stage, we can take the activities of L.P. Krysin, V.D. Bondaletov, G.A. Sudzilovsky. During this period, special dictionaries of slang were created under the editorship of O.P. Ermakov, E.A. Zemskaya, R.I. Rozina, V.S. Elistratov, and V.P. Korovushkin.

In Uzbek linguistics, a number of researches were conducted on this term. For example, in the second half of the 20th century, linguists Sh.Shoabdurahmanov and M.Askarova defined slang as "words and expressions that show class differences, and are understandable for upper class representatives. Jargon is defined as words taken from Uzbek language, sometimes from other languages (Arabic and Tajik languages). Therefore, slang is a special language created for the purpose of mutual communication due to the requirements of one's profession and interest. Jargon, unlike slang, is created in order to facilitate mutual communication in a certain professional sphere, to demonstrate a characteristic sign belonging to a certain profession. In its composition, there are speech elements typical of young people. Among them, in the language of cooks: to flatter the taste (gives a sweet, delicious taste), to curl the rice (to cook the pilaf in moderation), to cook alberto (to cook in the oven), to absorb the fat (to absorb the fat), etc.

Nowadays, slang is also used in artistic and journalistic style. Usually, slang, slang is used to express the uniqueness of the character's speech in fiction or to more reliably describe the criminal environment in the work. In addition, we witness the use of slang by sports commentators during the broadcast: we can find expressions such as cheated, passed around in the speech of the players. As a result, jargon began to be used in journalistic style. Recently, slang has expanded from a sociolinguistic indicator to an expressive stylistic function in written and oral speech. For example, to put the economy on a needle - posadit ekkonomiya na igloo (newspaper article) - in the sense of bringing the economy into crisis. By the end of the 20th century, slangs of this type began to be referred to as a separate interslang term: "Generally speaking, slang is defined as social dialect words used for a specific purpose in mass media and fiction, although the original source of use has weakened, but has not lost its stylistic color." At the same time, it is necessary to distinguish jargon from professional terms, because sometimes one is mistaken for the other. L.I. Skvortsov explained this misunderstanding, and it is necessary to distinguish professional terms from professional jargon and argo, although the terms are fully formed, have a strong development system and belong to a specific field.

They differ from slang in that they have a fixed meaning. Here are the differences between professional terms and slang:

1. Professional terms: 2. Professional jargon:
 - a) belonging to the literary class; a) belonging to a non-literary class;
 - b) object of linguistics; b) object of sociolinguistics;
 - c) the concept c) the concept is renamed;

- names: angishvona, like an example; yakan-money;
- g) speaker for a specific purpose g) speaker for a specific purpose
- does not apply; applies;
- d) the meaning does not change; d) the meaning is variable;
- e) structurally formed; e) not structurally formed.

Term (term) is an independent, large layer compared to jargon. It is distinguished by the fact that it is used in all styles and is an object of literary language. And social dialectic is a variable - unstable layer. For example: we can see that the concept of chief is used in the form of pakhan, knyaz in the 19th century, but in the late 20th century, it is used in the form of tut, shotut, and in the 21st century, it is used in the form of boss. That is, a concept changes its nominative function while keeping its semantics under the influence of time. This is one of the characteristics of sociolects. In addition, jargon differs from other types of social dialect and professional terms by being divided into internal groups: jargons used in the speech of palace officials - historical jargons: matqul etdi (died), rutbai olyi (new decree); slangs used in the speech of religious leaders - religious slangs: mahkur (to incur the wrath of Allah), shakhnatun najaf (guardian of the state); slang used in the speech of merchants: hat (premium price), fifty-six (silk); Jargons used in the speech of musicians (musicians): yakan (money), dry (no money), etc.

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